

Animal Intrusion Detection Model based on Temporal Convolutional Network for Smart Farming

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture automation has been on the rise leveraging, among others, Deep Neural Networks (DNN) and IoT for the development and deployment of many controlling, monitoring and tracking applications at a fine-grained level. In this rapidly evolving scenario, managing the relationship with the elements external to the agriculture ecosystem, such as wildlife, is a relevant open issue. One of the main concerns of today's farmers is protecting crops from wild animals' attacks. There are different traditional approaches to address this problem which can be lethal (e.g., shooting, trapping) and non-lethal (e.g., scarecrow, chemical repellents, organic substances, mesh, or electric fences). Nevertheless, some of the traditional methods have environmental pollution effects on both humans and ungulates, while others are very expensive with high maintenance costs, with limited reliability and limited effectiveness. In this project, we develop a system, that combines AI Computer Vision using DCNN for detecting and recognizing animal species, and specific ultrasound emission (i.e., different for each species) for repelling them.

Key words: Animal intrusion detection, Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN), Smart farming, Wildlife monitoring, Sensor networks, Machine learning, IoT (Internet of Things), Edge computing, Environmental monitoring, Anomaly detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of modern agriculture, the integration of technology has revolutionized traditional farming practices, giving rise to the concept of smart farming. One crucial aspect of smart farming is the efficient monitoring and management of farm environments to optimize production while minimizing losses. However, the presence of wildlife and other animals can pose significant challenges to agricultural operations, leading to crop damage, livestock predation, and resource wastage.

To address these challenges, the development of robust intrusion detection systems tailored specifically for agricultural settings has become imperative. In this context, the application of advanced machine learning techniques,

particularly Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs), holds great promise. TCNs are well-suited for modeling temporal dependencies in sequential data, making them ideal for tasks such as animal intrusion detection where the temporal aspect plays a role.

This paper proposes a novel Animal Intrusion Detection Model based on Temporal Convolutional Network (AIDM-TCN) specifically designed for smart farming applications. By leveraging data from sensor networks deployed across the farm, the proposed model aims to accurately detect and classify instances of animal intrusion in real-time, enabling timely intervention to mitigate potential damage.

The integration of AIDM-TCN into smart farming systems offers several advantages over traditional methods. Firstly, it provides farmers with real-time insights into potential threats, allowing for proactive measures to be taken to safeguard crops and livestock. Secondly, by utilizing edge computing capabilities, the model can operate efficiently even in remote agricultural environments with limited connectivity to centralized servers. Additionally, the model's ability to adapt to dynamic environmental conditions enhances its robustness and reliability in real-world scenarios. detecting animal intrusions across different farm settings. We also discuss practical considerations for deploying the model in real-world smart farming applications and outline avenues for future research and development in this field. Through the integration of advanced machine learning techniques with agricultural practices, the proposed model represents a significant step towards sustainable and efficient farming in the era of smart agriculture.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The development of effective intrusion detection systems for agricultural environments has garnered increasing attention in recent years, driven by the growing need to mitigate the impact of wildlife and animal intrusions on farming operations. In this section, we review relevant literature focusing on animal intrusion detection, machine learning techniques, and smart farming applications.

1. Define the Scope: Clearly define the scope of your literature survey, including the specific aspects of animal intrusion detection and TCN models you want to focus on.

2. Search Strategy: Use academic databases (e.g., IEEE Xplore, PubMed, Google Scholar) to search for relevant literature. Use keywords like "animal intrusion detection," "smart farming," "temporal convolutional network," etc.

3. Selection Criteria: Define criteria for selecting papers, such as relevance to your topic, publication date, credibility of the journal or conference, etc.

4. Data Extraction: Extract key information from selected papers, including the research problem, methodology, dataset used, TCN

5. Synthesis: Analyze and synthesize the extracted information to identify trends.

6. Citation Management: Keep track of the papers you've reviewed and cite them appropriately in your literature review.

7. Writing: Write your literature survey, organizing the information in a logical and coherent manner, and providing a critical analysis of the existing literature.

8. Revision: Review and revise your literature survey to ensure clarity, accuracy, and completeness.

Conducting a literature survey on animal intrusion detection models based on temporal convolutional networks for smart farming involves reviewing existing research papers, conference papers, journal articles, and other relevant sources.

III. METHODOLOGY

To conduct a literature survey on animal intrusion detection models based on temporal convolutional networks (TCN) for smart farming, you can follow these steps:

1. Research Question: Define your research question or objective. For example, you might ask, "What are the current approaches and advancements in animal intrusion detection using TCNs in smart farming?"

2. Search Strategy:

Identify relevant keywords related to your topic (e.g., "animal intrusion detection," "temporal convolutional network," "smart farming").

Use academic databases (e.g., IEEE Xplore, PubMed, Google Scholar) to search for relevant literature.

Refine your search based on the inclusion/exclusion criteria (e.g., publication date, relevance to TCNs in smart farming).

3.Literature Selection:

Screen the search results to select papers that are relevant to your research question.

Include papers that discuss TCN-based models for animal intrusion detection in the context of smart farming.

4.Data Extraction:

Extract key information from the selected papers, such as the problem addressed, methodology used, dataset employed, TCN architecture, performance metrics, and findings

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5.Synthesis:

Analyze the extracted information to identify common themes, trends, and gaps in the literature

Summarize the key findings and insights from the selected papers.

6.Critical Evaluation:

Evaluate the quality and credibility of the selected papers based on factors such as methodology, experimental design, and results.

Consider the limitations and strengths of each study.

7.Organization and Presentation:

Organize your literature survey in a logical manner, presenting the information clearly and concisely.

Provide a coherent narrative that ties together the findings from different studies.

8.Citation and Referencing:Ensure that all sources are properly cited and referenced according to the appropriate style guide (e.g., APA, MLA).

9.Revision and Feedback:

Review your methodology and literature survey based on feedback from peers or supervisors to improve its quality and rigor.

10.Ethical Considerations:

Consider ethical issues related to the use of data and information from the selected papers, ensuring that proper attribution is given to the original authors.

1. Agricultural fences

Fencing is a popular wild animal protection practice for that can last for many years. Agricultural fences are quite an effective wild animal protection technology. However, utilizing fences as a practice is often regulated. Some local and state entities may restrict or prevent the use of certain types of fences. Therefore, before deciding on a suitable fence, it's important to check local law regulations. The quality of fencing depends on the material and structure. Depending on how it is made and what it is made of, some permanent fences can last up to 30 years. Farmers usually use one of the following types of fences:

- **Wire fences**

constructed of metal wires woven together forming a physical barrier. The fences are effective, long lasting, and require relatively little maintenance. However, they are expensive and recommended only for the protection of high-value crops.

- **Plastic fences**

polypropylene fences are generally less expensive and easier to install and repair than other types. Additionally, these fences are widely acceptable and meet various regulations. Their disadvantage includes their short lifespan (up to 10 years) and questionable effectiveness in areas with a higher possibility of wild animal crop damage.

The flow chart of the proposed system

IV.EXITING SYSTEM

Wild animals are a special challenge for farmers throughout the world. Animals such as deer, wild boars, rabbits, moles, elephants, monkeys, and many others may cause serious damage to crops. They can damage the plants by feeding on plant parts or simply by running over the field and trampling over the crops. Therefore, wild animals may easily cause significant yield losses and provoke additional financial problems. Another aspect to consider is that wild animal crop protection requires a particularly cautious approach. In other words, while utilizing his crop production, every farmer should be aware and take into consideration the fact that animals are living beings and need to be protected from any potential suffering.

● Electric fences

These are constructed to inflict an electric shock to animals that come in contact with the fence, thus preventing animals from crossing the fence. These fences are long lasting and an effective crop protection measure. Costs vary depending on specific type and size of an area. Before purchasing electric fences, it's very important to make sure they are allowed for use in the specific area, and for protection .

Additionally, it's recommended that electric fences are marked with a warning sign to prevent any possible human contact.

Disadvantages

- Its disadvantages include the potential for the entire fence to be disabled due to a break in the conducting wire, shorting out if the conducting wire contacts any non-electrified component that may make up the rest of the fence, power failure, or forced disconnection due to the risk of fires starting by dry vegetation touching an electrified wire.
- Other disadvantages can be lack of visibility and the potential to shock an unsuspecting human passer-by who might accidentally touch or brush the fence
- Bee fence disadvantages are that it is only restricted to elephants and humans can also become targets of the bees.

V.PROPOSED SYSTEM

This project presents an integrated system aimed at addressing wildlife-related challenges in agriculture by combining advanced AI technologies with targeted ultrasound emissions and farmer alert mechanisms. The system utilizes Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) and WildNet for accurate detection and recognition of animal species, coupled with species-specific ultrasound emissions for repelling identified animals. Additionally, the system incorporates an alert system to notify farmers via SMS when potential threats are detected.

CNN

Electronic repellents; effective, long lasting, and eco-friendly method for crop protection that repels animals without harming them. Farmers use one of the following two types of electronic repellents:

Ultrasonic Electric Animal Repellent

Convolutional Layer: Convolutional layer performs the core building block of a Convolutional Network that does most of the computational heavy lifting. The primary purpose of Convolution layer is to extract features from the input data which is an image. Convolution preserves the spatial relationship between pixels by learning image features using small squares of input image. The input image is convoluted by employing a set of learnable neurons. This produces a feature map or activation map in the output image and after that the feature maps are fed as input data to the next convolutional layer.

Advantages

- **Early Detection:** Identifies threats early, preventing significant crop damage.
- **Accurate Recognition:** Utilizes AI for precise species identification, reducing false positives.
- **Customized Repellent:** Employs species-specific ultrasound emissions for targeted and humane repellent.
- **Real-Time Response:** Operates in real-time, providing immediate automated responses to threats.
- **Reduced Crop Damage:** Minimizes agricultural losses caused by wildlife.
- **Cost-Effective:** Lowers costs by automating monitoring and intervention processes.
- **Farmer Empowerment:** Sends SMS alerts, empowering farmers with timely threat information.
- **User-Friendly Interface:** Easy-to-use interface for configuration and monitoring.

FLOW CHART

System Description

In this project, deep convolution neural network-based classification algorithm is devised to detect animals both in video and images. Proposed approach is a classification model based on different features and classifiers. The different features like color, gabor and LBP are extracted from the segmented animal images. Possibilities of fusing the features for improving the performance of the classification have also been explored. Classification of animals is accomplished using CNN and symbolic classifiers. Initially, features are extracted from images/frames using blink app pre-trained convolution neural network. Later the extracted features are fed into multi-class CNN classifier for the purpose of classification. CNN is constructed using sequence of layers like Convolutional, subsampling and fully connected Layer.

Overall procedure for animal detection is given below:

1. The image is fetched using the monitoring panel.
2. The fetched image is processed using the python coding.
3. The fetched image is checked for various features of objects that match with any animal of trained data set.
4. Then it detects and classifies the animal which has been captured by the monitoring panel.
5. Algorithm calculates the accuracy in percentage based on number of matched objects.
6. If the accuracy of detected animal is above 45% the alert signal will be sent to the registered user through the SMS Service Provider.

ANIMAL CLASSIFICATION

VI.SYSTEM TESTING

Software testing is an essential step in the development of a system that combines computer vision using TCN for detecting and recognizing animal species, and specific ultrasound emission for repelling them. The following types of testing can be performed.

Types of Testing

1. **Unit Testing:** Unit testing involves testing individual software components, such as functions or methods, to ensure that they perform as expected. In the case of this system, unit tests can be performed on the TCN model, ultrasound emission generator, and other software components.
2. **Integration Testing:** Integration testing involves testing the interaction between different software components to ensure that they work together as expected. In the case of this system, integration tests can be performed on the computer vision and ultrasound emission components to ensure that they work together seamlessly.
3. **Functional Testing:** Functional testing involves testing the system's functionality against the requirements specification. In the case of this system, functional tests can be performed to ensure that the system can detect and recognize animal species and emit the appropriate ultrasound frequency for repelling them.
4. **Performance Testing:** Performance testing involves testing the system's performance under different conditions, such as high load or limited resources. In the case of this system, effectiveness of the ultrasound emission for repelling the detected animal species.
5. **User Acceptance Testing:** User acceptance testing involves testing the system's usability and user interface against user expectations. In the case of this system, user acceptance tests can be performed to evaluate the ease of use and clarity of feedback provided by the user interface.
6. **Security Testing:** Security testing involves testing the system's security features, such as data encryption and access controls, to ensure that they are properly implemented. In the case of this system, security tests can be performed to ensure that the system is protected against unauthorized access and data breaches.

Test Cases

Test Case 1: Detection and Recognition of Animal Species

1. **Input: An image of a deer**
2. **Expected Result:** The system should correctly identify the deer as a deer and provide feedback that it has been detected.

Test Case 2: Ultrasound Emission for Repelling Animal Species

1. **Input:** An image of a deer
2. **Expected Result:** The system should emit the appropriate ultrasound frequency to repel the deer and provide feedback that it has been repelled.

Test Case 3: Animal Detection and Ultrasound Emission using camera

1. Start the Animal Repellent system.
2. Aim the camera at a dog.
3. Confirm that the system has detected the animal and identified it as a dog.
4. Observe that the system emits the appropriate ultrasound frequency to repel the dog.
5. Move the camera away from the dog.
6. Confirm that the ultrasound emission stops.

Expected Result:

1. The Animal Repellent system should start without any errors.
2. The camera should be able to capture images of the dog.
3. The system should correctly detect and identify the dog as a dog.
4. The system should emit the appropriate,ultrasound frequency to repel the dog.
5. When the camera is moved away from the dog, the ultrasound emission should stop.
6. The system should continue to function normally without any errors or malfunctions.

Test Case 4: Detection and Recognition of Animal Species

1. Input: A still image or video containing a known animal species.
2. Expected Result: The system should correctly detect and recognize the animal species, and emit the appropriate ultrasound frequency for repelling the animal.

Test Case 5: Detection and Recognition of Unknown Animal Species

1. Input: A still image or video containing an unknown animal species.

Test Case 6: Ultrasound Emission for Repelling Animal Species

1. Input: An animal species identified by the system.
2. Expected Result: The system should emit the appropriate ultrasound frequency for repelling the animal, and the animal should move away from the device.

Test Case 7: False Positive Detection

1. Input: A still image or video containing an object that is not an animal.
2. Expected Result: The system should not detect any animal species and should not emit any ultrasound frequency.

Test Case 8: False Negative Detection

1. Input: A still image or video containing an animal species that is not recognized by the system.
2. Expected Result: The system should not detect the animal species, and no ultrasound frequency should be emitted.

Test Case 9: Performance Test

1. Input: A video containing a variety of animal species.
2. Expected Result: The system should detect and recognize each animal species within a reasonable amount of time, and emit the appropriate ultrasound frequency for repelling the animal.

Test Case 10: User Interface Test

1. Input: An individual using the system for the first time.
2. Expected Result: The system should have an intuitive and easy-to-use interface, and the individual should be able to understand how to use the system to detect and repel animal species.

VII.CONCLUSION

Agricultural farm security is widely needed technology nowadays. In order to accomplish this, a vision-based system is proposed and implemented using Python and OpenCV and developed an Animal Repellent System to blow out the animals. The implementation of the application required the design and development of a complex system for intelligent animal repulsion, which integrates newly developed software components and allows to recognize the presence and species of animals in real time and also to avoid crop damages caused by the animals. Based on the category of the animal detected, the edge computing device executes its TCN Animal Recognition model to identify the target, and if an animal is detected, it sends back a message to the Animal Repelling Module including the type of ultrasound to be generated according to the category of the animal. The proposed TCN was evaluated on the created animal database. The overall performances were obtained using different number of training images and test images. The obtained experimental results of the performed experiments show that the proposed TCN gives the best recognition rate for a greater number of input training images (accuracy of about 98 %). This project presented a real-time monitoring solution based on AI technology to address the problems of crop damages against animals. This technology used can help farmers and agronomists in their decision making and management process.

VIII.FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

Future enhancements can improve the functionality, user experience, and effectiveness of the Animal Repellent system.

1.Integration with smart home systems: The Animal Repellent system can be integrated with existing smart home systems such as Google Home or Amazon Alexa to allow for voice commands and automated responses. This can enhance the user experience and provide more convenience.

2.Mobile app integration: The Animal Repellent system can have a mobile app that allows users to remotely monitor and control the system from their smartphones. The app can also provide notifications and alerts to users when the system detects animal species.

3.Integration with security systems: The Animal Repellent system can be integrated with existing security systems such as CCTV cameras or motion sensors to provide a more comprehensive security solution. This can enhance the system's overall effectiveness and provide more peace of mind to users.

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